

MDTA: An efficient, scalable and fast Multiple Disjoint Tree Algorithm for dynamic environments

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ABSTRACT

Emerging applications such as telemedicine, the tactile Internet or live streaming place high demands on low latency to ensure a satisfactory Quality of Experience (QoE). In these scenarios the use of trees can be particularly interesting to efficiently deliver traffic to groups of users because they further enhance network performance by providing redundancy and fault tolerance, ensuring service continuity when network failure or congestion scenarios occur. Furthermore, if trees are isolated from each other (they do not share common communication elements as links and/or nodes), their benefits are further enhanced since events such as failures or congestion in one tree do not affect others. However, the challenge of computing fully disjoint trees (both link- and node-disjoint) introduces significant mathematical complexity, resulting in longer computation times, which negatively impacts latency-sensitive applications.

In this article, we propose a novel algorithm designed to rapidly compute multiple fully (either link- or node-) disjoint trees while maintaining efficiency and scalability, specifically focused on targeting the low-latency requirements of emerging services and applications. The proposed algorithm addresses the complexity of ensuring disjointedness between trees without sacrificing performance. Our solution has been tested in a variety of network environments, including both wired and wireless scenarios.

The results showcase that our proposed method is approximately 100 times faster than existing techniques, while achieving a comparable success rate in terms of number of obtained disjoint trees. This significant improvement in computational speed makes our approach highly suitable for the low-latency requirements of next-generation networks.

1. Introduction

The digital transformation, driven by the development and growth of communication infrastructures, is rapidly evolving and giving rise to new paradigms such as Internet of Things (IoT), or immersive technologies such as eXtended Reality (XR), among others [1,2]. These advances are placing unprecedented demands on network reliability, resilience, and, most critically, low latency, for which routes that communicate groups of users with each other are essential to deliver new services. In this context, efficient and fast traffic delivery to multiple users through multiple trees is becoming increasingly important to deliver new applications and services such as telemedicine, to perform surgery remotely between multiple expert surgeons from all over the world; Vehicle-to-everything (V2X), to communicate groups of autonomous vehicles in

order to be able to react quickly to unexpected events or obstacles; or on the tactile Internet where low-latency communication between groups of users is critical to emulate the real world and maintain Quality of Experience (QoE).

Focusing on classic networking scenarios, such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN), the use of multiple trees improves traffic management and resource allocation by separating the control and data planes, thus improving operational flexibility and the management of large data flows [3,4]. The use of multiple trees is also important in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), for example, in which multiple trees can be used to enable efficient communication between groups of sensors and actuators, optimizing power consumption and reducing latency in communications [5,6]. In the IoT paradigm, the use of multiple trees

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can support the efficient distribution of updates and data among connected groups of devices, optimizing spectrum and energy [7], which is critical for extending the life of small sensor batteries. In the upcoming 6G networks, which aim at ultra-high speeds and low latencies [8], the use of multiple trees can be critical to meet the vertical needs of the 6G. For instance, in the context of traffic and vehicular networks, vehicles may be physically distributed on multiple roads at different levels (for the same route and area) to avoid congestion [9], for which the use of multiple trees could also be leveraged to transmit disaggregated traffic information to vehicles at each level, or to transmit the same information to fleets of vehicles [10]. As another example, diverse sectors might benefit from remote worker operations, thanks to the low-latency 6G capabilities in conjunction with other technologies, such as XR [11,12], for which the use of trees can be useful to transport the information grouped between the operator and the end devices (machines, sensors, etc.).

While the broader concept of multiple paths is an ongoing research area with application in current and upcoming networks and paradigms, the advantage of applying multiple trees are significantly amplified when the trees are fully disjoint trees (i.e., trees do not share any elements between them). In particular, fully disjoint trees are particularly relevant in networking for several reasons:

1. **Load balancing:** Multiple disjoint trees enable the efficient delivery of data from one or more senders to multiple receivers on a network through multiple non-overlapping trees, optimizing network resource utilization and minimizing the network congestion.
2. **Resilience:** Disjoint trees provide greater fault tolerance and network resiliency by isolating trees from each other, which helps maintain uninterrupted data delivery between groups of users and improves network reliability.
3. **Scalability:** As the number of group members increases, they can be quickly added to various existing trees without the complex process of calculating and adding new routes.
4. **Quality of Service (QoS):** Disjoint trees can be optimized to support specific QoS requirements, enabling differentiated delivery and prioritization of multiple data based on the specific needs of applications or users.

However, despite the significant benefits of using fully-disjoint trees, the computation required to obtain such trees is highly complex and belongs to the NP-hard class of problems [13]. The difficulty of solving this problem leads to longer times to reach an optimal solution, as its complexity is influenced by several factors, including the network topology, the number of required paths, and the number of source and destination nodes. Current algorithms aim to maximize the number of discovered paths while minimizing their cost or length (min-max problem) [14,15], rather than prioritizing the optimization of the time required to obtain the solution. This may not be critical in some situations, but can be disastrous in the aforementioned dynamic and low-latency, scenarios in which load conditions are constantly changing and routing demands must be met as soon as possible to avoid impacting QoE. As an example, interactive applications are sensitive to delays greater than 100 or 150 ms [16], degrading the QoE beyond this limit. Therefore, proposals dedicated to the search of multiple disjoint trees in communication networks should provide results in lower times.

In this article, we propose Multiple Disjoint Tree Algorithm (MDTA), an algorithm tailored to address the problem of computing multiple fully disjoint trees fast and efficiently in a scalable manner. More specifically, MDTA not only computes fully disjoint trees two orders of magnitude faster than existing techniques, but it is also designed following a generalized approach so that it can be applied to both wired and wireless environments, and it is adaptable to different network topologies.

Therefore, the main design objectives of MDTA are:

1. To design an algorithm capable of computing multiple fully disjoint trees.
2. The algorithm should be able to be configured to compute both link-disjoint and node-disjoint algorithms.
3. The algorithm should compute the solution fast to meet the low latency requirements of next-generation applications and services.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows: Section 2 contains a review of the literature related to solutions for disjoint paths and trees; Section 3 describes the proposed algorithm and illustrates it with graphical examples to support it; Section 4 compiles the test performed to evaluate the algorithm, Section 5 discusses the applicability of the algorithm in the real world and practical scenarios, and finally, Section 6 summarizes conclusions and future work.

2. Related work

This section presents a review of the literature focusing on the multiple-disjoint-tree problem in data networks, driven by the demand for data services for which this problem is particularly well suited. It is divided into two sections according to the network typology: wired and wireless networks; and a final section that details the existing research gaps.

2.1. Wired networks

In wired networks, optical networking represents the preferred choice of Internet Service Providers (ISPs) when they come to upgrading legacy networks or deploying new ones due to their high speed of information transfer. Within optical networks, Wavelength-Division Multiplexing (WDM) and Elastic Optic Networks (EONs) techniques play an important role, enabling the parallel transmission of multiple data streams over the same physical medium using multiple wavelengths. This physical infrastructure, combined with multicast techniques, facilitates the efficient allocation of resources for data transmission to user groups. In these types of networks, fiber cuts are a recurrent problem, causing service interruptions that degrade the provided service. To quickly resolve sporadic link failures in multicast applications, a solution could be to protect multicast sessions from a single link failure, as suggested by [17–20]. However, if more than one failure occurs, these solutions are not valid, and strong protection schemes such as link-disjoint trees should be provided. Specifically, Singhal et al. [21] explore various multicast protection schemes from single link failure to a fully link-disjoint tree protection scheme by using custom algorithms or applying an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) technique. ILP is a mathematical optimization solution used to solve problems that can be expressed with integer variables and are solvable in polynomial time (NP-complete problem) [22]. This causes ILP to be widely leveraged for disjoint tree search problems, as in [23,24] to obtain a link-disjoint backup multicast sessions, or in [25] where an ILP is specifically designed for static scenarios to obtain a link-disjoint multicast tree to the primary tree and, also, an alternative heuristic solution for dynamic scenarios is also proposed. Heuristic algorithms are also a frequent solution for generating link-disjoint trees, as in [26,27], which provide greedy methods to solve various protection schemes.

Link-disjoint trees offer significant advantages beyond mere backup solutions serving, for example, as a versatile tool for improving performance and resource utilization. Specifically, Yang et al. [28], offer two ILP strategies that effectively maximize the service to a larger number of clients by assigning two disjoint trees to the same wavelength. This approach not only increases the efficiency of wavelength utilization but also expands the capacity of the network to serve more users simultaneously. Similarly, Alhusein et al. [29] propose an heuristic method inspired by biological bee food search to balance the load of the network, ensuring optimal resource allocation and preventing network

congestion. Furthermore, the work presented in [30] highlights the importance of using link-disjoint multicast trees for load balancing in the context of modern network architectures. Using both ILP and heuristic techniques to route traffic and allocate network functions, this research demonstrates how disjoint trees can be strategically deployed within a SDN-enabled Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) framework to meet the high demands of traffic users in the core of 5G networks and beyond.

Specifically, SDN emerged to provide flexibility and dynamism to networks through their management and programmability from a logically centralized device, the SDN controller. Alongside SDN, NFV has revolutionized networking by decoupling network functions from proprietary hardware. In this type of networks, link-disjoint trees are used to balance load by isolating traffic between trees by using heuristics [31]. However, this proposal is focused on simple data center network topologies with a regular structure and only with two or three hierarchical levels. For more complex data center networks, such as cubic topologies, Zhang et al. [32] propose a recursive link-disjoint spanning tree computation algorithm applied to fault-tolerant communication. Due to the complexity of computing complete disjoint trees, other authors aim at a solution based on maximally-disjoint redundant trees to ensure that streams are carried without interruption from a source to multiple destinations by sending redundant content through such redundant trees [33,34]. Moreover, for the sake of simplicity, other authors do not look for disjoint trees in SDN-NFV scenarios and focus solely on the use of trees using different techniques, such as heuristics or ILP [35–39].

2.2. Wireless networks

The exponential growth of IoT networks, and consequently wireless networks, is driven by today's ultraconnected society's demand for Internet access with an ever-increasing array of devices. This surge underscores the need for research on disjoint trees in wireless networks, highlighting their central role in improving network performance and reliability. Tamar et al. [40] focus on ad-hoc wireless networks to design a technique that provides multiple completely or partially disjoint routes improving the throughput and delay ratio of certain ad-hoc routing protocols, such as Ad-hoc On-demand Distance Vector (AODV) [41], but worsening the packet delivery ratio. Continuing with ad-hoc networks, but in the context of WSNs, some works focus on obtaining multiple node-disjoint paths for improving the reliability and efficiency of the network [42,43]. There are also proposals that leverage SDN as an enabling technology for ad-hoc networks in smart grids as, for instance, Popovic et al. [44], who design several algorithms to obtain multiple node-disjoint trees to ensure the reliability against node failures while increasing network utilization efficiency and minimizing the forwarding rules required in SDN switches.

Power consumption is a major concern for wireless networks, especially large-scale ones, due to the energy required to transmit data. Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANETs) are an example of this type of network in which the nodes form a mesh and act as routing nodes to facilitate traffic routing. These nodes are typically powered by batteries of limited capacity, which limits their lifetime due to the high power requirements of wireless transmissions. Efficient power management is therefore essential to prolong network functionality and ensure reliable communications in MANET environments. Specifically, to provide multi-objective optimization in terms of minimizing energy consumption and improving network lifetime, Velusamy et al. [45] design a multi-objective function that provides node-disjoint paths with respect to existing solutions as Dynamic Source Routing (DSR) [46]. There are also proposals that focus specifically on the disjoint routing problem to save energy and extend the lifetime of wireless devices [47,48].

Vehicular Ad-Hoc Networks (VANETs), a special subset of MANETs, have received considerable attention for the use of specifically Internet-connected vehicles as network nodes. Unlike traditional MANETs,

where power consumption is a primary challenge, VANETs shift the focus to managing the impact of vehicle mobility. This mobility introduces unique constraints and challenges for network dynamics, requiring customized approaches to ensure reliable communications despite the high-speed movement of nodes within the network. Precisely, MalekiTabar et al. [49] focus on VANETs together with SDN to provide node-disjoint multipath routes appropriately adapted to the continuous topological changes and interruptions suffered in VANETs due to vehicle mobility, and responding to the increasing traffic demands. They provide a three-step methodology consisting of a compilation of topological information, a second path calculation that considers link utilization, residual bandwidth, and vehicle stability; and a final route assignment by priority according to the requirements of the application.

2.3. Research gaps

Our review of the state of the art yields three main gaps in the field: (1) the solutions are very specific and dependent on particular deployments and topologies, (2) the methodologies employed to calculate those solutions are often time consuming and not practical in highly dynamic scenarios, and (3) few works exist that build disjoint trees (as most works focus on disjoint paths or routes) and, from those, many provide partial disjointness and, at most, two disjoint trees (usually a main one and another acting as backup).

Furthermore, link-disjoint trees are common in wired networks due to their infrastructure, while node-disjoint trees are preferred in wireless environments. This trend eventually results in customized solutions that are incompatible between different network types. Methods such as ILP and heuristics, while accurate, are slow and unsuitable for the low-latency requirements of next-generation networks (e.g., maximum control to meet the needs of ultra-reliable services such as tactical Internet is between 10 and 20 milliseconds [50]).

Our proposal, MDTA, effectively addresses these gaps by efficiently computing more than two disjoint trees, either link- and node-disjoint, as requested, and faster than other existing approaches. Its computational speed makes it well-suited for emerging low-latency paradigms, in which traditional methods like ILP or heuristic approaches are inadequate due to the significant time required to compute a solution. Furthermore, MDTA's capacity to calculate more than two disjoint trees expands its applicability to a wider range of use cases, in contrast to most existing solutions that are restricted to the computation of only two disjoint trees. Lastly, its ability to compute both link- and node-disjoint trees makes it a versatile solution for diverse scenarios.

3. Multiple disjoint tree algorithm

This section introduces MDTA, an algorithm focused on the fast computation of multiple fully link- or node-disjoint trees. Firstly, this section offers a high-level description of the algorithm and details the motivations for its development. Subsequently, the focus shifts to provide a detailed description of its operation to compute the multiple fully-disjoint trees in a procedure divided into two phases: a first analysis of costs phase and a second disjoint tree computation phase.

3.1. Algorithm overview

MDTA is conceived as an evolution of the Multiple Disjoint Path Algorithm (MDPAlg) [51] specifically tailored to the computation of disjoint trees, instead of single source–destination paths. That is, in MDPAlg, disjointness is guaranteed only for the paths belonging to a source–destination node pair, which might result in diverse network elements (links or nodes) being shared between paths of different source–destination node pairs. In contrast, the challenge in MDTA goes a step beyond, because it focuses on computing fully-disjoint trees (which, at the same time, are comprised of multiple source–destination node pairs). Basically, the disjoint tree problem can be seen

Fig. 1. General system model workflow of MDTA.

as the search for acyclic subgraphs connecting the source node with the multiple destinations, so the combinatorial complexity to obtain disjoint trees is higher than to calculate disjoint paths. The selection of MDPAlg as the foundational algorithm is due to its simplicity and strong performance in identifying multiple disjoint paths, as well as its favorable computational complexity and fast convergence time to reach a solution. Consequently, it serves as a solid foundation for addressing more complex challenges, such as the computation of disjoint trees.

MDTA follows a two-phase process as its predecessor MDPAlg. A system model workflow of the MDTA algorithm with its two-phase process is shown in Fig. 1. As input parameters, MDTA has the mode of operation of the algorithm, the destination nodes, the source node and the topological graph of the network. First, the algorithm obtains these inputs and processes them. Then MDTA leverages the topological graph and the source node to execute the first phase of the algorithm, in which, a cost analysis of the topology, from the source node, is

performed by running a modified version of Dijkstra’s algorithm. This version stores additional cost information compared to the original Dijkstra’s algorithm. Specifically, it evaluates and computes, from a given source node (S) the aggregated cost incurred from that source node to each remaining node in the graph through all its neighbors, providing a complete characterization of the topological graph. This information is stored in the *Cost Matrix (CM)* and returned once the first phase finalizes, as depicted in Fig. 1. Later, MDTA executes the second phase incorporating the information about the source and destination nodes, and the operation mode (link- or node-disjoint) to the previously computed *CM*. In this second phase, MDTA derives multiple link- or node-disjoint trees among S, and the set of destination nodes. These trees are stored and returned in a new matrix named *Tree Matrix (TM)*.

This design allows MDTA to compute multiple (link- or node-) disjoint trees in a single run, speeding up the computation time and avoiding the need to iteratively perform multiple runs of an algorithm taking into account the previously computed trees to ensure tree disjointness.

Once the overview is complete, the next two sections describe each phase of the MDTA in more detail. In addition, the source code of the algorithm is available in the repository [52].

3.2. First phase: Analysis of costs

As previously anticipated, a complete characterization of the graph is done by running a modified version of Dijkstra’s algorithm that computes the cost incurred of going, from the given source node S, to any other node in the graph via any available link.

Algorithm 1 Dijkstra’s algorithm

```

1: function DIJKSTRA’SALGORITHM( $G, s$ )
2:   Initialize( $V, P$ )
3:    $Cost = Initialize\_single\_source(G, s)$ 
4:    $Q = Get\ nodes\ from\ G$ 
5:   while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
6:      $u = extract\_min(Q)$ 
7:     Insert  $u$  in  $V$ 
8:     for each vertex  $v$  neighbor of  $u$  do
9:        $R \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{if } V \cap v = \emptyset \text{ then} \\ \quad w = L_c \text{ from } u \text{ to } v \\ \text{if } Cost(u) + w < Cost(v) \text{ then} \\ \quad Cost(v) = Cost(u) + w \\ \quad P(v) = u \end{array} \right.$ 
10:  return  $Cost, P$ 

```

Algorithm 2 Analysis of costs of MDTA

```

1: function ANALYSISOF COSTS( $G, s$ )
2:
3:    $CM = Initialize\_single\_source(G, s)$ 
4:    $Q = Get\ nodes\ from\ G$ 
5:   while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
6:      $u = extract\_min(Q)$ 
7:
8:     for each vertex  $v$  neighbor of  $u$  do
9:        $R \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{if } v \neq s \text{ then} \\ \quad w = L_c \text{ from } u \text{ to } v \\ \text{if } CM[u][u] + w < CM[v][v] \text{ then} \\ \quad CM[v][v] = CM[u][u] + w \\ \quad CM[u][v] = CM[u][u] + w \end{array} \right.$ 
10:  return  $CM$ 

```

To facilitate the comparison of Dijkstra’s algorithm with the first phase of MDTA, Algorithms 1 and 2 present their pseudocode in

Fig. 2. Analysis of cost phase of MDTA.

parallel, whose high-level code structure is taken from the definition of Dijkstra’s algorithm of [53]. Dijkstra’s algorithm returns two vectors, *Cost* and *P*, which contain the minimum-cost of going from *S* to any other node and the parent node (predecessor) through which the minimum-cost was computed, respectively. Building the minimum-cost tree from this information is straightforward, but requires additional steps. Therefore, only a single tree can be obtained by running Dijkstra’s algorithm, so if multiple disjoint trees are needed, multiple runs of Dijkstra’s algorithm with the subsequent tree construction steps are required.

With respect to MDTA, it uses a more sophisticated data structure, *CM*, to store the complete characterization of the network. In fact, *CM* merges the information of Dijkstra’s *Cost* and *P* vectors and adds some more information of the remaining links of the graph to achieve it. Specifically, *CM* contains the accumulated cost incurred to go from the source node to the remaining nodes in the graph. The structure of *CM* is a square matrix of $N \times N$, being N the number of nodes in the graph.

After explaining the data structures, the comparison between Dijkstra’s algorithm and the first phase of MDTA is detailed with the high-level pseudocode of Algorithms 1 and 2. It can be seen that both algorithms take the same input parameters, a graph (G) and a given source node (s). Furthermore, both start with the initialization of variables, which in the case of Dijkstra’s algorithm includes the vectors V , Q , P and $Cost$, while in the case of MDTA, it corresponds to the variables CM and Q . Vectors V and Q keep track of the nodes analyzed (visited nodes) and those awaiting evaluation (unvisited nodes), respectively. P and $Cost$ record parent node relationships and their accumulated costs from s in the minimum-cost tree. They are exactly the two outputs of Dijkstra’s algorithm, as previously stated. On the other hand, CM stores the accumulated cost from s not only in the minimum-cost tree, but also in all remaining links of the graph, as abovementioned, while Q is shared with Dijkstra’s algorithm. Furthermore, the vector $Cost$ in Dijkstra’s algorithm and CM in MDTA are initially set to infinity for all

entries except for the one corresponding to s , which is set to zero as the starting node.

Once set up, both methods iteratively examine each node in the graph once, prioritizing their selection based on cost policies, selecting from Q (unvisited nodes) the node with the lowest-cost at each iteration. Dijkstra’s algorithm employs the *RELAX* function, as originally described by Cormen et al. [53], to compute the cumulative cost incurred to go from s to the destination node through all of its neighbors, and then selects the neighbor that provides the lowest-cost. MDTA modifies the *RELAX* function to include additional information about the remaining links in the graph, which are not considered in Dijkstra’s algorithm, to provide a comprehensive characterization of the graph in just one data structure, the *CM*. These adjustments include storing the accumulated cost incurred from s to reach the destination nodes through all their neighbors, not just the best. Consequently, although both methods follow a similar analysis procedure, MDTA preserves more information about the graph than Dijkstra’s algorithm.

To better understand the procedure of the analysis of cost phase of MDTA, a graphical example is provided in Fig. 2. The topological graph of the example has 7 nodes, of which node S is the given source node where the analysis of cost phase starts. The upper half of the figure shows the graph of the network with the nodes and the links that connect them. In addition, each link is labeled with the cost of traversing it. The bottom half contains how the *CM* is filled by MDTA in the first tree steps of the algorithm (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2c), and the final result (Fig. 2d). *CM* contains the cost incurred to go from S to any other in the graph via any link, as mentioned above. The way in which the information is stored is as follows: the columns represent end nodes and the rows represent intermediate nodes that allow reaching end nodes. The number contained in each cell is the accumulated cost incurred from the source node (S) to reach the end node (column) via the intermediate node (row). Moreover, there are different cells shadowed. The gray cells of the column S are disabled because S is the source node

and cannot be an end node. Purple cells represent unvisited nodes and contain the minimum accumulated cost of the unvisited node, while blue cells represent visited nodes and contain the lowest accumulated cost of the visited node. When a cell is blue, the cost is the lowest possible and no longer changes because the node is visited.

Fig. 2a shows the *CM* after the first iteration of the algorithm. The algorithm starts the analysis from the source node *S* by applying the function *RELAX* to each of the neighbors of *S* (the nodes *A*, *B*, *C*). After this operation, the row *S* of the *CM* was filled and the cost to go from *S* to *A*, *B*, *C* is 2, 1, 2 respectively. Furthermore, since there is no more information, the minimum-cost associated with the nodes *A*, *B*, *C* was updated on the diagonal of the *CM*. Fig. 2b contains the result of the second iteration. Now, *B* was selected as minimum-cost node to evaluate, as it has the minimum-cost of the unvisited nodes (the diagonal of *CM* in Fig. 2a). Therefore, the algorithm marked it as visited (represented as a blue cell on the diagonal of Fig. 2b), and applied the *RELAX* function to all its neighbors. The result of this process is shown in the row *B* of *CM*. A concrete example for better understanding is the cell in row *B* column *A*, which contains the accumulated cost incurred to go from *S* to *A* via *B*. This cost was obtained as the cost to go from *S* to *B* (1, as reflected in the blue cell on the diagonal), plus the cost to go from *B* to *A* (the link cost between *A*-*B* is 2), resulting in a final cost of 3. In addition, when this new cost is obtained, the algorithm evaluated if it reduced the accumulated cost of *A* by comparing the previous minimum-cost of *A* (2, indicated in the cell of the diagonal *A*,*A*). As the new cost is higher than the previous value (3 versus 2), the value of the diagonal cell *A*,*A* is not updated. However, for nodes *D*,*E*,*F* the value is updated as their previous cost was infinite. Fig. 2c contains the result of the third iteration. In this case there were two unvisited nodes with minimum-cost, *A* and *C*, as it can see on the diagonal of *CM* in Fig. 2b, therefore the algorithm selected the first of them *A*. The procedure is similar to the previous case, all the neighbors of *A* were evaluated, the row *A* was filled, and if any minimum-cost of the neighbors was reduced, its value was updated. In this case, the value of the cell *D*,*D* was updated from 8 to 3. Finally, the complete characterization of the graph after the analysis of cost phase is shown in Fig. 2d.

3.3. Second phase: Disjoint trees construction

This section describes the process followed by MDTA to compute the set of disjoint trees from the information previously gathered in *CM*. First, the section presents the pseudocode of this second phase, to later exemplify and describe in detail each of the operating modes of MDTA in two dedicated subsections: link-disjoint (Section 3.3.1), and node-disjoint (Section 3.3.2).

According to the description of Algorithm 3, it takes as input parameters the source node (*s*), the destination nodes (*D*), *CM*, the operation mode (*op_mode*), and the maximum number of disjoint trees to compute (*t*). As a result, it returns the matrix *TM* that contains information about the disjoint trees computed, from which it is easy to obtain the list with the nodes that belong to them. Among the input parameters, the user can define the destination nodes, the operation mode and the maximum number of disjoint trees, while the source node and *CM* come from the previous phase of the algorithm.

The algorithm starts by initializing the variables *previous*, *next_hop*, *new_branch* and *Tree*, used during the tree construction process. The first two allow adding new branches to the trees in a sequential way from destination nodes towards *s*, while the last two store the branch of the tree under construction and the whole tree once it is finished. Afterwards, the algorithm calls the function *Conversion* to sort the information contained in the *CM* matrix, so that each node has its neighbors classified in ascending order according to the previously calculated cumulative cost. Fig. 3 illustrates this process. The upper half of the figure shows the *CM* derived from the first phase and the ordering of each neighbor based on their cost. For example, in the column *A*, the node *S* is the neighbor with the highest priority, as it has a cost of 2,

Fig. 3. Conversion process from CM to TM.

later the node *B* with a cost of 3, and then the node *D* with a cost of 4. The same process applies to the rest of the nodes. The final result is the matrix *TM*, which is shown in the lower half of the figure. In addition, *TM* has several parallel planes (one per tree) to keep the information of each tree isolated.

Once the *TM* is created, the function starts the tree construction process iteratively for each disjoint tree *t*. Specifically, in each tree, the process consists of adding new branches from each destination node stored in *D*. Branching starts at the destination nodes and continues by selecting lower-cost available neighbors until the given source node is reached. In broad terms, these intermediate steps are represented between lines 6 and 16 of the algorithm, being the function *GetMinCostNeighbor* the responsible for advancing and selecting the lowest-cost neighbor available at each step, while the variables *previous* and *next_hop* keep the traceability of given hops in the branch under construction. When the source node is reached, the branch is complete and consolidated in *TM* (line 14). At that point, a new branch construction process starts from the next destination node (line 6). Finally, when all branches are finished, the tree is complete and a new tree construction process is started for the next disjoint tree (line 4).

During this process, disjointedness is provided by the function *ApplyDisjointednessRestrictions* (line 10), which modifies *TM* at each step depending on the mode of operation (link- or node-disjoint), ensuring disjointedness between trees. In particular, for the link-disjoint operation mode, the function bonuses the link between *previous* and *next_hop*, in both directions, for the plane *t* of *TM*, and deletes the same cells in the *t-1* remaining planes of *TM*. In this sense, it is ensured that new branches added to the existing tree *t* are uniquely attached to such a tree, while the links used by this tree *t* cannot be selected by the remaining *t-1* trees. For node-disjoint the function also bonuses both directions of the link between *previous* and *next_hop*, but deletes *next_hop* node in the *t-1* remaining planes to ensure that such node is not chosen in any other tree. Sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 contain illustrative examples to better understand these procedures.

There is also a go-back mechanism provided by the function *GoBack* (line 16) to explore alternative vias to reach the source node if the branch construction process arrives at a dead end (there is no valid next hop). In such a case, the function goes back through the branch under construction until an alternative is found. Finally, when the process is finished and all the disjoint trees are computed, the function returns the matrix *TM* from which the list of disjoint trees is obtained directly.

Algorithm 3 Disjoint trees construction process

```

1: function DISJOINTTREESCONSTRUCTION( $s, D, CM, op\_mode, t$ )
2:   Initialize_variables(previous, next_hop, new_branch)
3:    $TM = Conversion(CM, t)$ 
4:   for each disjoint tree  $t$  do
5:     while  $D \neq \emptyset$  do
6:        $dst = ExtractNode(D)$ 
7:        $next\_hop = GetMinCostNeighbor(TM, dst, t)$ 
8:       while  $next\_hop \neq s$  do
9:         Advance : previous = next_hop; next_hop = GetMinCostNeighbor(TM, previous, t)
10:        ApplyDisjointnessRestrictions(TM, op_mode, previous, next_hop, t)
11:        if  $next\_hop \neq 0$  then
12:          Insert(next_hop, new_branch)
13:        if  $next\_hop == s$  then
14:          Consolidate(new_branch, TM, t)
15:        if  $next\_hop == \emptyset$  then
16:          GoBack(TM, previous, next_hop, t)
return  $TM$ 

```

3.3.1. Link-disjoint tree example

Fig. 4 shows an example of the link-disjoint tree construction procedure in the same topology example used before. The figure is divided vertically, following the same structure as in Fig. 2, with the upper half of the figure showing the graph and the lower half illustrating the steps that MDTA performs to compute the procedure for building the link-disjoint trees. S is the source node, and B, F are the destination nodes (in purple), so MDTA searches multiple link-disjoint trees between $S-[B, F]$. In this example, 3 link-disjoint trees are computed, whose construction process is represented in three separate subfigures: Fig. 4a for the first tree, Fig. 4b for the second and Fig. 4c for the third. Each subfigure illustrates the steps contained between lines 5 and 16 of the Algorithm 3.

The blue color represents all the actions of the first tree, orange for the second, and green for the third. Moreover, TM is shown with all its planes in parallel to visualize how the disjointedness is applied to all the trees. For each tree, the active plane belonging to the tree under construction is highlighted in TM in purple.

The algorithm starts to build the first branch of the first tree from the first destination node, the node B . This process is represented in Fig. 4a with a solid blue line. Node B , selects as next hop the lowest-cost neighbor available in the column B of TM , so chooses the first cell available, being the node S the next hop node.

To ensure link-disjointedness, the algorithm reserves the link used to go from B to S (represented as a blue circle in the first row of the column B), and disables the same cell in the rest of the dimensions (represented by a color smoothing of the cell S^*). In this way, the link $S-B$ is not eligible anymore by other trees. As S is the source node, the first branch is complete and the algorithm starts a new branch construction process from the second destination node, the node F . The process for the second branch of the first tree is represented by a blue dotted line. The algorithm begins to build the branch from F selecting its lowest-cost neighbor, (first cell of column F), the node B , reserving the corresponding cell in the first plane of TM , and disabling the same entry in the rest of dimensions (marked as B^*). Moreover, to guarantee that the trees are completely disjoint, the reverse direction of the link (from B to F) it is also disabled in all the planes of TM (the 5th row of the column B , with F^*). This way the link $B-F$ cannot be chosen by other trees or branches. Then the algorithm evaluates the situation from the node B and, since B has a branch directly connected to S , the algorithm connects this second branch to the previous one, thus completing the construction process of the first link-disjoint tree. Once the first tree is ended, the algorithm starts the procedure for the second tree, represented in Fig. 4b. As in the previous tree, the solid line represents the branch construction process from the first destination node, and the dotted line represents the process from the second one.

The process is similar to the first tree, but the algorithm now operates in the dimension of TM reserved for the second tree. Again, the algorithm starts to build the first branch of the second tree from the node B , choosing the node C as the lowest-cost available neighbor of the node B , since the lowest one (the node S) was previously chosen by the first tree and it is not available. Again, to ensure the disjointedness, in the second plane, the 3rd row of the column B is reserved for the second tree (marked with an orange rectangle), and the same cell is disabled in the rest of the planes. There is also disable the reverse direction of the link (the 2nd row of column C) to ensure disjointedness between the trees. The algorithm continues from the node C choosing the lower cost available neighbor, the node S (1st row of column C), and applies the disjointedness constraints. Once the source node is reached, the first branch of the second tree ends and the construction of the second branch of the second tree from the second destination node, F , starts. This branch construction process goes from the node F through the node C ending at the node S and, again, the same disjointedness constraints seen before are applied in each step (from F to C first, and then from C to S).

Finally, the third tree construction procedure starts when the second tree ends. The process is illustrated in Fig. 4c. The process is identical to the previous ones, being the first branch of the third tree composed by the nodes B, A, S , and the second branch of the third tree from the second destination node composed by the nodes F, E, B, A, S . Again, the disjointedness constraints are applied in each step.

3.3.2. Node-disjoint tree example

Fig. 5 provides an example of the node-disjoint tree construction procedure in the same scenario seen before. The example uses the same structure, nomenclature, iconography, and colors as the link-disjoint example. Again, each subfigure illustrates the steps to construct each disjoint tree, corresponding to the lines between lines 5 and 16 of the Algorithm 3. The difference lies in the disjointedness conditions used to ensure node-disjoint trees instead of link-disjoint trees. Fig. 5a shows the procedure for constructing the first branch of the first tree. The process starts at the destination node B by selecting its lower-cost neighbor, the node S (the 1st row of the column B), and later applying the disjointedness restrictions. As mentioned above, the requirements for guaranteeing node-disjoint trees change. In node mode, any node added to a tree is disabled in the rest of the planes of TM that do not belong to such a tree, to avoid its selection for future trees. In this example, as the node B belongs to the first tree, it is disabled in the planes for the second and third trees (the cells of TM marked as B^* in soft blue in the planes Tree2 and Tree3). Therefore, the construction of the first branch of the first tree ends because the process reached the source node S . The second branch of the first tree starts at the

Fig. 4. Link-disjoint tree construction process in MDTA.

Fig. 5. Node-disjoint path construction process in MDTA.

destination node F by selecting as lowest-cost available neighbor the node B . To ensure disjointness, in the first plane, the 1st row of the column F is reserved for the first tree (marked with a blue circle), and the same cell is disabled in the planes for the second and the third tree with F^* . Moreover, since F belongs to the first tree, it is also disabled in the planes of Tree2 and Tree3. The algorithm then evaluates the situation from the node B and, since B has a branch directly connected to S , the algorithm connects this second branch to the previous one, thus completing the construction process of the first node-disjoint tree.

The processes for the second and the third disjoint tree are identical, selecting the lowest-cost neighbor in each step, disabling the node added to the path in all the planes except in the plane of the tree under construction, and disabling the reverse link in the plane of the tree under construction.

4. Evaluation

This section presents the results obtained by MDTA and compares them with alternative proposals. Since MDTA is a versatile algorithm that can compute node- and link-disjoint trees, both modes are evaluated. On the one hand, the link-disjoint operation mode is tested in wired scenarios, while the node-disjoint mode is tested in wireless scenarios. This decision follows the trends observed in the related work examined in Section 2. For a comprehensive understanding of the performed tests, this section is divided into three parts: a first subsection that presents the system details (hardware architecture and simulation software used) and a general description (the topologies used in each test, general characteristics, and associated confidence intervals); a second subsection that focuses on the presentation and analysis of the link-disjoint mode in wired networks; and a third subsection that contains the results of the node-disjoint mode results in wireless networks, as well as an additional test for this mode that evaluates the node-disjoint tree search in a topology with connectivity constraints, due to the more stringent requirements needed by this mode to find node-disjoint trees.

All results of Section 4, and associated source data, are stored and publicly available in the GitHub repository of the author's research group [52].

4.1. System details and description of the experiments

Our simulation platform test is comprised of a homogeneous infrastructure consisting of a set of 8 computers powered by Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 with 24 GB of RAM and the installation of the MATLAB simulation tool. MATLAB was selected as the platform to implement and simulate the different algorithms because of its power and versatility aimed at scientists and engineers, with fast deployment and debugging tools and good performance.

Regarding the tests carried out, two topologies were used, derived from the analysis of related works: the USNET topology (Fig. 6a), and an ad-hoc wireless topology (Fig. 6b). The first topology, USNET, is a well-known real fiber optic topology, widely used in works dealing with WDMs, and EONs networks in conjunction with SDN technology; accordingly, it was selected for this testbed for link-disjoint mode. The second topology, the ad-hoc topology, was chosen from Popovic et al. [44] since they use such a topology to compute the node-disjoint trees; for that reason, this topology is tested in the node-disjoint mode. In all tests performed, two disjoint trees were computed because of the limitations imposed by MDTA's competitors, whose design constraints limit them to obtaining only two disjoint trees. However, as explained in Section 3, MDTA can compute more than two disjoint trees.

Regarding the characteristics of the tests, multiple replications of each test were performed, with the resultant mean values and the corresponding 95% confidence intervals presented in the results displayed. In addition, several metrics were collected, such as average cost, number of complete disjoint paths obtained, time to compute the solution, among others.

4.2. Wired scenario

The first experiment evaluated MDTA working in link-disjoint mode in the USNET topology under the WDM networks paradigm because they provide cost-effective and high-speed network architectures [54]. The work of Singhal et al. [21] was selected for comparison because it proposes various mechanisms to provide multiple session protection schemes in WDM networks, ranging from protection schemes for disjoint paths between pairs of nodes, to fully link-disjoint trees, and evaluated them in the USNET topology. Specifically, they provide:

- Arc-disjoint protection schemes: Links can be shared in opposite directions. Their proposals are PPH_FLD & MPH_LDT algorithms.
- Segment disjoint: Each link has an alternative disjoint backup link, but the conjunction of backup links could not form a path. Their proposals are PPH_SDS, MPH_SDS, OPP_SDS_PPH and OPP_SDS_MPH algorithms.
- Link-disjoint paths: Paths that do not share links between a source node and a destination node. Their proposals are OPP_SDP algorithm and an ILP method.
- Link-disjoint trees: Two trees that connect a source to multiple destinations do not share links. Their proposals are PPH_FLD and MPH_LDT.

Our MDTA fits into this last category, making it a competitor to the PPH_FLD and MPH_LDT algorithms. In addition, they provide a mathematical formulation to solve the problem optimally by using ILP.

To comprehensively compare our algorithm with Singhal's, we also implemented the ILP method from the description provided in Singhal et al. [21] to solve the link-disjoint tree problem. This method is hereinafter referred to as and Singhal's ILP. We chose the same platform to test MDTA and Singhal's ILP (MATLAB) in order to maintain a uniform evaluation criterion to ensure a fair comparison to prove the actual performance results of both algorithms.

We replicated the experiments carried out by Singhal's, consisting of generating random multicast connections between a source and multiple destinations to compute two link-disjoint trees. The source and destination nodes are randomly selected from the topology. The number of destinations determines the session size, which ranges from 1 to the maximum number of nodes in the topology minus one (because the source node is also in the topology). From each run, two link-disjoint trees were obtained, and each run was repeated 5000 times. In addition, the average values and the 95% confidence intervals are shown in the results.

We collected several metrics to compare the results for both algorithms, including: blocking probability, measured as the percentage of the solutions found in which either one or the two disjoint trees do not reach all the destinations (Fig. 7); the percentage of destinations served by both disjoint trees when blocking occurs and it is unfeasible to offer two link-disjoint trees to all the destinations (Fig. 8); the average cost of the trees, calculated as the sum of the cost of the links used by both disjoint trees (Fig. 9); and the computational time required to solve the problem (Fig. 10). We analyze all of them within the following subsections.

4.2.1. Blocking probability

The first metric analyzed is the probability of blocking, which measures the success or failure of establishing two trees for all destinations. In each run, if the algorithm does not provide two disjoint trees for each node, the blocking probability for such a run is 100%, otherwise it is 0%. Later, for each session size, the average values and 95% confidence intervals are computed, whose results can be shown in Fig. 7.

The graph shows the results for MDTA and Singhal's ILP, represented by the solid and dotted lines, respectively.

It can be seen that the blocking probability grows exponentially as the size of the session increases. This is a normal behavior, since the larger the number of destination nodes in the session size, the smaller

Fig. 6. Topologies used for the evaluation in wired (left) and wireless (right) scenarios.

Fig. 7. Blocking probability in USNET.

Fig. 8. Percentage of destinations served over session size in USNET.

the number of links available to build new branches for the disjoint trees. This effect also occurs in the remaining specific solutions of Singhal’s for computing disjoint trees (PPH_LDT and MPH_LDT), reaching about 40% of the blocking probability with 8 active sessions. The rest of proposals in Singhal’s achieve lower blocking probabilities because they provide disjoint arcs, segments, or paths, instead of fully link-disjoint trees, and thus do not satisfy the stricter constraints required in a link-disjoint tree problem.

In any case, it is important to note that MDTA outperforms Singhal’s results (PPH_LDT, MPH_LDT and Singhal’s ILP). This is due to the design of the MDTA algorithm. In the second phase, when the disjoint trees are built, the decisions are made locally based on the information of the node (the next hop is chosen taking into account the neighbor node free with lower cost). Therefore, if nodes with lower connectivity are processed first, the nodes with more connections are available to complete the disjoint trees later and the search space is larger to find the solution.

Therefore, the limitations found on the blocking probability, when the two link-disjoint trees are not served to all destinations, are due to the scope and constraints of the problem and the resources available to add new branches to the trees. Anyway, MDTA is better than Singhal’s results in terms of blocking probability.

4.2.2. Percentage of destinations served by two trees

To provide more information and complement the meaning of the results obtained for the blocking probability, it is interesting to analyze the percentage of destinations (over the session size) that are eventually served by both link-disjoint trees, when blocking occurs. Both the first and second are complementary metrics; while the first one calculates the percentage of trees that cannot be completely calculated according to each algorithm, the second showcases the effect of that blocking, that is, how many nodes are served by two trees.

Specifically, Fig. 8 illustrates this metric, again comparing MDTA with Singhal’s ILP. As can be observed, in the worst case, when the session size contains all network nodes (one acting as a source and the rest as destinations), with MDTA still the 80% of the destinations are served by two trees, leaving the remaining 20% with a single tree, while with Singhal’s ILP the 75% of destinations are served with 2 trees. Again, MDTA allows more destinations to be served with the two disjoint trees.

4.2.3. Cost of the trees

Regarding the third measured metric, the cost of the trees, Fig. 9 shows the accumulated cost of both trees (primary and secondary). It can be observed that both MDTA and Singhal’s ILP, are in the same range of values. When comparing them, the cost obtained by

Fig. 9. Average cost of both trees in USNET.

MDTA is slightly higher than Singhal's ILP because MDTA bonuses the calculation speed at the expense of obtaining slightly longer paths. However, the graphs tend to flatten as the session size increases; hence, for large sessions, all available links in the topology are used to provide the disjoint trees.

4.2.4. Time to solve the problem

Finally, the solving time is analyzed. Fig. 10 depicts the time required to compute the disjoint trees using both MDTA and Singhal's ILP. The results show that there is a dramatic difference between MDTA and Singhal's ILP. MDTA reduces the time to solve the problem by about two orders of magnitude with respect to Singhal's ILP, being MDTA much faster in finding the solution. Furthermore, this tendency remains stable throughout the test, regardless of the size of the session. Therefore, MDTA proves to be a scalable solution that outperforms other solutions in terms of the quality of the computed disjoint trees and also significantly reduces the time needed to compute the solution, making it a suitable algorithm for dynamic scenarios where multiple disjoint trees need to be allocated quickly to meet the latency requirements that new network services and applications demand.

4.3. Wireless scenario

This second experiment was carried out to test MDTA in the context of IoT environments, where WSN is a promising technology for low-cost network monitoring and efficient energy consumption. MDTA was compared to Popovic's [44] because they provide node-disjoint trees in a SDN context for WSN. From Popovic's, the Steiner solution was chosen for comparison with MDTA because, as Popovic's indicates, their Steiner solution provides the minimum total cost and it also offers a good trade-off between practicality (implementation considerations) and performance (time complexity and cost of the resulting trees), as it is inspired by the Takahashi-Matsuyama algorithm [55]. This method is hereinafter referred to as Popovic's Steiner.

Our evaluation proof replicated Popovic's test. The same random ad-hoc random topology as Popovic's was used, shown in Fig. 6b. More specifically, 100 nodes were randomly placed in the topology grid, a square of 100 m x 100 m, satisfying the constraint that the distance between nodes is at least 75 m. In addition, the cost of all links was set at 1, as in the original test [44]. The source nodes were randomly selected from the grid and assigned a traffic rate uniformly distributed in the interval [0.025, 0.05] Erlang, while destinations were also randomly selected from the grid, with a guaranteed distance of at least 100 m between each pair of destinations. Tree allocation was

Fig. 10. Time required to compute solution in USNET.

performed to ensure that the maximum capacity of the links was not exceeded. Each trial was run 20 times, as in the Popovic's test, and the average values and 95% confidence intervals are depicted in the results.

In addition to this first test, a second test was performed for the wireless scenario. Both MDTA and Popovic's Steiner solution were launched in the USNET topology, replicating the test of Section 4.2 (wired scenario), since the limited connectivity of the USNET topology places greater demands on node-disjoint algorithms. The objective was to evaluate the effectiveness of these algorithms in a more challenging environment, where it is more complex to find a feasible solution in low-connectivity topologies.

Again, MATLAB was the platform for comparing MDTA and Popovic's Steiner to provide a consistent evaluation criteria that ensures a comprehensive comparison of the results.

The results collected for both algorithms were the same as in the original work of Popovic [44], that is, the number of sources placed (Fig. 11), the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the minimum and the maximum number of hops (Figs. 12 and 13). Furthermore, we also evaluated the time required to compute the solution (Fig. 14), which is not provided in the original paper. Following the same structure as in the previous section, each result is presented in its own subsection.

4.3.1. Number of sources placed

This metric analyzes the number of sources allocated taking into account the resources available in the topology. When a node-disjoint tree is requested, the algorithm attempts to allocate two node-disjoint trees that guarantee disjointness and traffic load requirements. If there are not enough resources, the source of the node-disjoint trees cannot be placed.

Fig. 11 shows the number of sources placed by MDTA and Popovic's Steiner in the ad-hoc random topology. From the graph, it can be concluded that Popovic's Steiner algorithm slightly outperformed MDTA, allocating about 8%–30% more destinations than MDTA. This is because Popovic's Steiner finds the minimum total cost, while MDTA finds the solution based on local node cost information by selecting the minimum local at each step, which increases the number of hops, but speeds up the computation because the branch tree selection is very fast.

4.3.2. Number of hops

The second metric is focused on measuring the number of minimum and maximum hops per tree. Specifically, Figs. 12 and 13 show the difference between making global or local decisions in the tree

Fig. 11. Sources placed in random ad-hoc topology.

Fig. 12. Minimum number of hops in random ad-hoc topology.

Fig. 13. Maximum number of hops in random ad-hoc topology.

Fig. 14. Time required to compute the solution in random ad-hoc topology.

construction process. When the minimum number of hops is analyzed (Fig. 12), Popovic’s Steiner and MDTA got similar results because these trees were built at the beginning, when there are multiple choices to construct the trees. However, trees with maximum hops are usually obtained at the end, when the possibilities to build new disjoint trees are limited by the previously obtained trees. In this situation (Fig. 13), Popovic’s Steiner got shorter trees than MDTA due to their global search basis, while MDTA unperformed because it produces longer trees due to its local selection policy, which reduces the search space for future node-disjoint trees more.

4.3.3. Time to solve the problem

Finally, the third metric evaluates the time taken to compute the trees. Once again, MDTA demonstrated its superiority in the speed of solution computation, significantly reducing the time required to generate node-disjoint trees compared to Popovic’s Steiner, as can be observed in Fig. 14. In particular, it achieved a reduction in computation time of more than two orders of magnitude, being much faster in providing the disjoint trees, making it suitable for dynamic real-time environments where the traffic allocation should be done very quickly.

4.3.4. Stressing the node-disjoint tree search

As previously anticipated, in order to stress the algorithms, the link-disjoint tests were repeated in the USNET topology for Popovic’s

Steiner and MDTA working in node-disjoint tree mode. The random ad-hoc topology is a highly connected topology that favors the search for disjoint trees, while USNET is a low connected topology, so the search for node-disjoint trees is challenging, and algorithms are stressed to demonstrate their performance in critical scenarios.

For that reason, the tests of Section 4.2 were repeated for MDTA working in node-disjoint mode and Popovic’s Steiner under the same conditions as the original test (destination session sizes, number of runs, etc.).

Fig. 15 presents the comparative analysis of the blocking probability associated with MDTA and Popovic’s Steiner algorithms over different session sizes. Again, the results show an exponential increase in blocking probability as a function of session size, which is significantly more pronounced compared to the results of the link-disjoint mode shown in Fig. 7. This is due to the stricter requirements of the node-disjoint tree definition, which directly reduces the number of feasible node-disjoint trees available in the network (as compared to link-disjoint trees), whose insight in the results is the higher blocking probability. Regarding the comparative results of the algorithms, MDTA obtains better results, since it slightly reduces the blocking probability with respect to Popovic’s Steiner.

According to the results shown in Fig. 16, MDTA demonstrates the ability to provide two disjoint trees to approximately 60% of the destinations in the worst-case scenario with sessions of 23 destinations, which significantly outperforms the results of Popovic’s Steiner, which covers only a 15% under the same conditions. This significant difference can be attributed to the inherent search methods employed by

Fig. 15. Blocking probability in USNET for node-disjoint tree mode.

Fig. 17. Average cost per tree in USNET for node-disjoint tree mode.

Fig. 16. Percentage of destinations served over session size in USNET for node-disjoint tree mode.

Fig. 18. Resolution time in USNET for node-disjoint tree mode.

each algorithm: the strategy of Popovic’s Steiner focuses on expanding the search radius from the source node, thereby initially limiting the potential search area, while, in contrast, MDTA incrementally adds new branches to existing trees, extending the trees from the destinations back to the source. Thus, MDTA does not only offers a lower blocking probability than Popovic’s Steiner, but also serves more destinations with two disjoint trees, obtaining better results in topologies with limited connectivity.

On the other hand, MDTA tends to produce longer trees than those produced by Popovic’s Steiner algorithm, which is supported by the consistently higher cumulative cost depicted in Fig. 17. This is due to the local decisions made by MDTA, as opposed to the global solution approach of Popovic’s Steiner.

Finally, and aligned with previous tests, the time required by MDTA is again approximately two orders of magnitude smaller than the time required by Popovic’s Steiner, as illustrated in Fig. 18.

Again, MDTA shows its potential by being much faster than its competitor and improving the results when computing node-disjoint trees in topologies with restricted connectivity.

5. Discussion

5.1. Applications and comparison with related algorithms

As previously stated, scalability and low-latency are critical factors in future networks, such as 6G, which must accommodate the demands

of new applications and services [56]. Furthermore, the anticipated massive influx of devices and connections into the network necessitates the use of scalable algorithms capable of computing routes for large-scale networks in a short amount of time. In this context, MDTA has demonstrated its efficacy in computing multiple disjoint trees, maintaining scalability as the network size increases. Given that MDTA achieves computation times of 1–10 ms for 24-node networks (i.e., implying the construction of trees with up to 23 destination nodes), it is well suited to meet the latency requirements of latency-stringent applications, such as deterministic networks (critical services like fire detection or network failure should not exceed 10 ~ 50 ms) [57], Virtual Reality (VR) and XR applications (under 10 ~ 50 ms for immersive environments and to prevent user vertigo) [58] or telesurgery (under 10 ms for patient safety) [59]. In contrast, ILP and Steiner’s algorithm require substantially longer computation times, ranging from 100 ms to 1 s, rendering them impractical for latency-sensitive applications.

5.2. Implications in real scenarios

Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the evaluation of MDTA in this study was conducted through simulations. While simulation was selected as an appropriate tool for extensive comparison using different parameters, and also because existing related work had also been tested via simulation, results could vary in real-world

deployments. More specifically, the effective time required to establish the trees might be higher due to the additional overhead of external mechanisms needed to detect and update network topology changes, as well as mechanisms to install routing rules in network devices, for example. Both of them potentially introduce delays that contribute to the overall route computation and installation time. For instance, a topology discovery mechanism for a network of 27 nodes is approximately 0,7 ms [60], while the installation of routing rules might require up to 120 ms [61]. Specific research works aim to tackle the challenge of reducing those times, and MDTA is agnostic to the leveraged method of discovery and/or rule installation, so it can adapt to the most suitable one for each scenario.

Additionally, in terms of the physical infrastructure suitable for deploying such algorithms, MDTA is specifically designed for centralized networks, where a master element has the full control and visibility of the network topology. This central element is responsible for updating the topology, executing the route calculation algorithm (MDTA in our case), and installing the rules on affected devices. Softwarized network environments (combining SDN and/or NFV) are particularly well-suited for this role, providing the necessary framework for deploying MDTA in real-world environments. More specifically, MDTA could be implemented as a piece of software (Java, C, Python) whose input would be any topology obtained by the discovery service, and whose output would yield the different forwarding rules to update in the network.

Based on this analysis, MDTA emerges as a strong candidate to address the requirements of next-generation networks. Its ability to compute disjoint trees efficiently and rapidly, combined with its adaptability to different scenarios, makes it particularly suitable for real-time and latency-sensitive deployments based on softwarized networks, like the future 6G deployments.

6. Conclusion

This paper introduces MDTA, a fast algorithm designed to compute both link- and node-disjoint trees in a procedure structured in two phases: a first phase focused on gathering topological data using a refined modification of Dijkstra's algorithm; and a second phase that computes the multiple disjoint trees using the data generated in the second phase. The algorithm prioritizes the computation speed in the second phase by selecting the local minimum-cost solution that ensures disjointedness in each step, enabling it to swiftly acquire the disjoint trees. This attribute makes it a favorable solution for dynamic environments in which rapid traffic assignment is imperative.

Furthermore, because of its agnostic nature, it can be easily adapted to different contexts. In particular, due to its adaptability, MDTA was tested both in wired WDM networks because they are cost-effective and high-speed architectures, and in wireless networks, WSNs in the context of IoT, because of their low-cost network monitoring and efficient energy consumption. The versatility of MDTA makes it be able to compute multiple fully-disjoint trees, instead of computing only two fully-disjoint trees, a limitation found in the related works for most of the analyzed proposals. It can also add new destination nodes to previously discovered trees just by running the second phase, reducing the time required to extend existing trees.

Regarding the performance of MDTA, in all scenarios MDTA obtained similar results in terms of blocking probability, percentage of served destinations and average cost of the trees, while requiring much less time to compute the results (showcasing a difference of two order of magnitude), which reaffirms the speed of computation of MDTA and shows its potential for dynamic and massive environments. Precisely, the time consumed by algorithms to compute the disjoint trees is a measure that is usually hidden in recent works that use optimization techniques such as ILP, or heuristics, due to their high times to calculate the solution, making them incompatible with dynamic scenarios that require fast traffic allocation, for which MDTA is indeed very adequate.

As a result, MDTA emerges as a dynamic and universally applicable algorithm that quickly computes multiple link- or node-disjoint trees, minimizing computation and response times. Its agnostic design allows it to be applied to any scenario that can be modeled with a graph, from existing network paradigms, such as wired networks and WSN, to several diverse areas, such as evacuation systems and power grids, among others. This versatility and speed highlight the importance and potential impact of our proposal in modern network environments and other scenarios. However, MDTA, as most of route computation algorithms, depends on an external topology update process to provide a new set of updated trees. Likewise, if the topology connectivity is constrained or poor, MDTA might not be able to provide a complete set of disjoint trees, and some destinations might only belong to a subset of the computed disjoint trees.

As for the experiments conducted, they were simulated in a controlled environment with Matlab, because it is a rapid development tool that allows to reproduce scenarios close to real world. In this sense, this simulation environment helps to characterize the behavior of the algorithms under study and to estimate the behavior they are likely to exhibit in a real environment. While these experiments might not entirely reflect the actual performance characteristics of the algorithms under study, they still provide a realistic approximation of their performance, which allows to evaluate whether it is worthwhile to implement them in real hardware.

In future work, we plan to implement and deploy the algorithm in a real network environment using hardware equipment from the laboratories of Cisco and Colt. Similarly, its application in alternative areas, such as path planning in evacuation systems and logistics transport routes is being considered. Furthermore, a secondary iteration of the algorithm is being investigated to ensure full service coverage to all destinations, particularly in scenarios where physical topological constraints prevent the computation of fully disjoint trees. This is achieved through the expedited computation of maximally partially disjoint trees.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Diego Lopez-Pajares: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elisa Rojas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mankamana Prasad Mishra:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Parveen Jindgar:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Joaquin Alvarez-Horcajo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Nicolas Manso:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Jonathan Desmarais:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] I. Cisco Systems, Cisco annual internet report (2018–2023) white paper, 2020, <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/collateral/executive-perspectives/annual-internet-report/white-paper-c11-741490.html>, (Accessed 30 June 2024).
- [2] L. Huawei Technologies Co., Communications networks 2030, 2020, https://www-file.huawei.com/-/media/corp2020/pdf/giv/industry-reports/communications_network_2030_en.pdf, (Accessed 30 June 2024).
- [3] D. Kreutz, F.M.V. Ramos, P.E. Verissimo, C.E. Rothenberg, S. Azodolmolky, S. Uhlig, Software-defined networking: A comprehensive survey, *Proc. IEEE* 103 (1) (2015) 14–76, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2014.2371999>.
- [4] T. Nadeau, K. Gray, *SDN: Software Defined Networks*, second ed., O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2021.
- [5] I.F. Akyildiz, W. Su, Y. Sankarasubramaniam, E. Cayirci, *Wireless sensor networks: A survey* (updated), *Comput. Netw.* 190 (2021) 107955.
- [6] C.-Y. Chong, S. Kumar, *Sensor networks: Evolution, opportunities, and challenges* (updated), *Proc. IEEE* 109 (4) (2021) 556–567.
- [7] L.D. Xu, W. He, S. Li, *Internet of Things in industries: A comprehensive survey*, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inform.* 15 (6) (2019) 4312–4325.
- [8] W. Saad, M. Bennis, M. Chen, *A vision of 6G wireless systems: Applications, trends, technologies, and open research problems*, *IEEE Netw.* 34 (3) (2020) 134–142.
- [9] A. Brummer, R. German, A. Djanatliev, *Modeling V2X communications across multiple road levels*, in: 2019 IEEE 2nd Connected and Automated Vehicles Symposium, CAVS, 2019, pp. 1–5, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/CAVS.2019.8887793>.
- [10] G. Chai, W. Wu, Q. Yang, F.R. Yu, *Data-driven resource allocation and group formation for platoon in V2X networks with CSI uncertainty*, *IEEE Trans. Commun.* 71 (12) (2023) 7117–7132, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TCOMM.2023.3311455>.
- [11] E. Anastasiou, A.T. Balafoutis, S. Fountas, *Applications of extended reality (XR) in agriculture, livestock farming, and aquaculture: A review*, *Smart Agric. Technol.* 3 (2023) 100105, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atech.2022.100105>.
- [12] D. Mourtzis, J. Angelopoulos, *Development of an extended reality-based collaborative platform for engineering education: Operator 5.0*, *Electronics* 12 (17) (2023) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/electronics12173663>.
- [13] K. Fleszar, M. Mnich, J. Spoerhase, *New algorithms for maximum disjoint paths based on tree-likeness*, *Math. Program.* 171 (2018) 433–461, URL <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10107-017-1199-3>.
- [14] F. Iqbal, F.A. Kuipers, *Disjoint paths in networks*, *Wiley Encycl. Electr. Electron. Eng.* (2015) 1–11, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/047134608X.W8254>.
- [15] C.-L. Li, S.T. McCormick, D. Simchi-Levi, *The complexity of finding two disjoint paths with min-max objective function*, *Discrete Appl. Math.* 26 (1) (1990) 105–115.
- [16] I. Vidal, I. Soto, *Multimedia networking technologies, protocols, and architectures*, Artech House Communications and Network Engineering Series, Artech House, 2019, URL <https://books.google.es/books?id=5GtNvgEACAAJ>.
- [17] X. Wang, S. Wang, L. Li, Y. Song, *Achieving resource reduction for protecting multicast sessions in WDM mesh networks*, *Photonic Netw. Commun.* 15 (2008) 131–140, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S11107-007-0102-1/METRICS>.
- [18] A. Frikha, S. Lahoud, B. Cousin, *Candidate-cycle-based heuristic algorithm for node-and-link protection of dynamic multicast traffic in optical DWDM networks*, in: *The International Conference on Information Network 2012*, IEEE, 2012, pp. 47–52, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICOIN.2012.6164347>.
- [19] C.K. Constantinou, G. Ellinas, K. Manousakis, *Survivability of multicast requests in mesh optical networks*, in: *2014 International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modeling*, IEEE, 2014, pp. 7–12.
- [20] B. Mohapatra, K. Sain, *Protecting multicast sessions against single-link failure in survivable WDM mesh networks*, in: *Data and Communication Networks: Proceedings of GUCON 2018*, Springer, 2019, pp. 69–82, URL https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-13-2254-9_7.
- [21] N.K. Singhal, L.H. Sahasrabudde, B. Mukherjee, *Provisioning of survivable multicast sessions against single link failures in optical WDM mesh networks*, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 21 (2003) 2587–2594, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JLT.2003.819550>.
- [22] A. Schrijver, *Theory of linear and integer programming*, *Wiley-Interscience Series in Discrete Mathematics and Optimization*, Wiley, 1999, pp. I–XI, 1–471.
- [23] S. Khanam, V. Dey, M. Chatterjee, U. Bhattacharya, *An offline cost-efficient strategy for multicast traffic protection in WDM optical mesh networks to aid rapid recovery*, *Opt. Switch. Netw.* 34 (2019) 47–57, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/J.OSN.2019.05.002>, backup link-disjoint segment by ILP and preconfiguring in WDM networks create primary paths and get link-disjoint backup paths..
- [24] P.D. Choudhury, S. Aparajita, D. Bharti, M. Singh, T. De, *A protection and fragmentation management approach in elastic optical networks under multicast traffic*, *Photonic Netw. Commun.* 46 (2023) 34–49, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S11107-023-00999-X/FIGURES/29>.
- [25] T. Gao, W. Zou, X. Li, B. Guo, S. Huang, B. Mukherjee, *Distributed sub-light-tree based multicast provisioning with shared protection in elastic optical datacenter networks*, *Opt. Switch. Netw.* 31 (2019) 39–51, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.osn.2018.08.003>.
- [26] R. Gościń, M. Kucharzak, *On the efficient optimization of unicast, anycast and multicast flows in survivable elastic optical networks*, *Opt. Switch. Netw.* 31 (2019) 114–126, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.osn.2018.10.010>.
- [27] S.Y. Mehr, B. Ramamurthy, *Protection techniques using resource delayed release for SDN-based OTN over WDM networks*, *Opt. Switch. Netw.* 51 (2024) 100762, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/J.OSN.2023.100762>.
- [28] W.-L. Yang, C.-T. Yang, Y.-C. Huang, *Optimal and heuristic algorithms for all-optical group multicast in resource-constrained WDM networks*, *Int. J. Commun. Syst.* 29 (15) (2016) 2292–2312, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/dac.3165>.
- [29] O. Alhussein, P.T. Do, Q. Ye, J. Li, W. Shi, W. Zhuang, X. Shen, X. Li, J. Rao, *A virtual network customization framework for multicast services in NFV-enabled core networks*, *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.* 38 (6) (2020) 1025–1039, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JSAC.2020.2986591>.
- [30] O. Alhussein, P.T. Do, Q. Ye, J. Li, W. Shi, W. Zhuang, X. Shen, X. Li, J. Rao, *A virtual network customization framework for multicast services in NFV-enabled core networks*, *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.* 38 (6) (2020) 1025–1039, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JSAC.2020.2986591>.
- [31] O. Rottenstreich, J. Yallouz, *Edge-disjoint tree allocation for multi-tenant cloud security in datacenter topologies*, *IEEE/ACM Trans. Netw.* (2024) 1–17, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNET.2024.3364173>.
- [32] H. Zhang, Y. Wang, J. Fan, Y. Han, B. Cheng, *Constructing edge-disjoint spanning trees in several cube-based networks with applications to edge fault-tolerant communication*, *J. Supercomput.* 80 (2024) 1907–1934, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S11227-023-05546-Z/TABLES/3>.
- [33] C. Colombo, F. Lepage, R. Kopp, E. Gnaedinger, *Two SDN multi-tree approaches for constrained seamless multicast*, in: *2018 IEEE International Conference on Computational Science and Engineering, CSE, IEEE, 2018*, pp. 77–84.
- [34] C. Colombo, F. Lepage, R. Kopp, E. Gnaedinger, *Seamless multicast: an SDN-based architecture for continuous audiovisual transport*, *Telecommun. Syst.* 78 (2021) 187–202, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S11235-021-00796-9/TABLES/1>.
- [35] A. Craig, B. Nandy, I. Lambadaris, P. Ashwood-Smith, *Load balancing for multicast traffic in SDN using real-time link cost modification*, in: *2015 IEEE International Conference on Communications, ICC, IEEE, 2015*, pp. 5789–5795.
- [36] S. Kotachi, T. Sato, R. Shinkuma, E. Oki, *Multicast routing model to minimize number of flow entries in software-defined network*, in: *2019 20th Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium, APNOMS, IEEE, 2019*, pp. 1–6.
- [37] J.I. Naser, A.J. Kadhim, *Multicast routing strategy for SDN-cluster based MANET*, *Int. J. Electr. Comput. Eng.* (2088-8708) 10 (5) (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp4447-4457>.
- [38] W. Gong, L. Pang, J. Wang, M. Xia, Y. Zhang, *A social-aware K means clustering algorithm for D2D multicast communication under SDN architecture*, *AEU-Int. J. Electron. Commun.* 132 (2021) 153610, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.aeue.2021.153610>.
- [39] H. Li, L. Wang, Z. Zhu, Y. Chen, Z. Lu, X. Wen, *Multicast service function chain orchestration in SDN/NFV-Enabled networks: Embedding, readjustment, and expanding*, *IEEE Trans. Netw. Serv. Manag.* 20 (4) (2023) 4634–4651, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSM.2023.3257187>.
- [40] A. Temar, M. Guezouri, N. Mbarek, *A new way of achieving multi-path routing in wireless networks*, *Int. J. Wirel. Mob. Comput.* 18 (2020) 90–100, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJWMC.2020.104772>.
- [41] S.R. Das, C.E. Perkins, E.M. Belding-Royer, *Ad hoc on-demand distance vector (AODV) routing*, (3561) 2003, <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC3561>.
- [42] S. Chakraborty, S. Chakraborty, S. Nandi, S. Karmakar, *Fault resilience in sensor networks: distributed node-disjoint multi-path multi-sink forwarding*, *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.* 57 (2015) 85–101, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2015.07.014>.
- [43] S.M.G. R.J. D'Souza, G. Varaprasad, *Digital signature-based secure node disjoint multipath routing protocol for wireless sensor networks*, *IEEE Sens. J.* 12 (10) (2012) 2941–2949, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2012.2205674>.
- [44] M. Popovic, R. Khalili, J.Y.L. Boudec, *Performance comparison of node-redundant multicast distribution trees in SDN networks*, 2017 *Int. Conf. Netw. Syst. NetSys 2017* (2017) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/NETSYS.2017.7903946>.
- [45] B. Velusamy, K. Karunanithy, D. Sauveron, R. Akram, et al., *Multi-objective function-based node-disjoint multipath routing for mobile ad hoc networks*, *Electronics* (2021) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/electronics10151781>.
- [46] H.A. Ali, M.F. Areed, D.I. Elewely, *An on-demand power and load-aware multi-path node-disjoint source routing scheme implementation using NS-2 for mobile ad-hoc networks*, *Simul. Model. Pract. Theory* 80 (2018) 50–65, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2017.09.005>.
- [47] S. Benakappa, M. Kiran, *Energy aware stable multipath disjoint routing based on accumulated trust value in MANETs*, *IJCNIS* 14 (2022) 14–26, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5815/ijcnis.2022.04.02>.
- [48] A. Pai H, K.K. Almuzaini, L. Ali, A. Javeed, B. Pant, P.K. Pareek, R. Akwafo, et al., *Delay-driven opportunistic routing with multichannel cooperative neighbor discovery for industry 4.0 wireless networks based on power and load awareness*, *Wirel. Commun. Mob. Comput.* 2022 (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2022/5256133>.
- [49] M. MalekiTabar, A.M. Rahmani, *A delay-constrained node-disjoint multipath routing in software-defined vehicular networks*, *Peer-to-Peer Netw. Appl.* 15 (2022) 1452–1472, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S12083-022-01304-9/FIGURES/15>.

- [50] T. Adame, M. Carrascosa-Zamacois, B. Bellalta, Time-sensitive networking in IEEE 802.11 be: On the way to low-latency WiFi 7, *Sensors* 21 (15) (2021) 4954, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s21154954>.
- [51] D. Lopez-Pajares, E. Rojas, J.A. Carral, I. Martinez-Yelmo, J. Alvarez-Horcajo, The disjoint multipath challenge: Multiple disjoint paths guaranteeing scalability, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 74422–74436, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3080931>.
- [52] NetIS Universidad de Alcalá, MDTA source code, 2024, <https://github.com/NETSERV-UAH/MDTA>, (Accessed June 2024).
- [53] T.H. Cormen, C.E. Leiserson, R.L. Rivest, C. Stein, *Introduction to algorithms, second ed.*, MIT Press, ISBN: 0070131511, 2001, p. 1180.
- [54] D. Chadha, *Optical WDM Networks: From Static to Elastic Networks*, John Wiley & Sons, 2019, p. 392.
- [55] H. Takahashi, An approximate solution for the steiner problem in graphs, *Math. Japon.* (1980) 573–577.
- [56] S. Mumtaz, V.G. Menon, M.I. Ashraf, Guest editorial: Ultra-low-latency and reliable communications for 6G networks, *IEEE Commun. Stand. Mag.* 5 (2) (2021) 10–11, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MCOMSTD.2021.9464926>.
- [57] E. Grossman, Deterministic networking use cases, in: Request for Comments, (8578) RFC Editor, 2019, <http://dx.doi.org/10.17487/RFC8578>.
- [58] Y. Siriwardhana, P. Porambage, M. Liyanage, M. Ylianttila, A survey on mobile augmented reality with 5G mobile edge computing: Architectures, applications, and technical aspects, *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutor.* 23 (2) (2021) 1160–1192, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2021.3061981>.
- [59] A. Behravan, V. Yajnanarayana, M.F. Keskin, H. Chen, D. Shrestha, T.E. Abrudan, T. Svensson, K. Schindhelm, A. Wolfgang, S. Lindberg, H. Wymeersch, Positioning and sensing in 6G: Gaps, challenges, and opportunities, *IEEE Veh. Technol. Mag.* 18 (1) (2023) 40–48, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MVT.2022.3219999>.
- [60] L. Ochoa-Aday, C. Cervelló-Pastor, A. Fernández-Fernández, eTDP: Enhanced topology discovery protocol for software-defined networks, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 23471–23487, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2899653>.
- [61] R. Aryan, A. Yazidi, F. Brattensborg, Øivind Kure, P.E. Engelstad, SDN spotlight: A real-time OpenFlow troubleshooting framework, *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.* 133 (2022) 364–377, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2022.03.014>.

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